

Conference of Academies for Applied Studies in Serbia (CAASS)
University Business Academy in Novi Sad, Faculty of Contemporary
Arts, Belgrade

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

International Multidisciplinary Conference
"Challenges of Contemporary Higher Education" - CCHE 2024
Kopaonik January 29th - February 3rd 2024
Vol_2

edited by:

Dr Branko Savić, professor

Belgrade, 2024

Impressum

Book of Proceedings, International Multidisciplinary Conference
"Challenges of Contemporary Higher Education" - CCHE 2024
Kopaonik January 29th - February 2nd 2024 <https://cche.rs/>

Editor

Dr Branko Savić, professor

Publisher

Conference of Academies for Applied Studies in Serbia (CAASS)
Bulevar Mihaila Pupina 2,, Novi Beograd, Serbia <https://www.caass.rs/>
University Business Academy in Novi Sad
Faculty of Contemporary Arts, 12 Svetozara Miletića Street, Belgrade, Serbia www.fsu.edu.rs

Cover design

Information Technology School ITS -Belgrade

Composition

Conference of Academies for Applied Studies in Serbia (CAASS)
Information Technology School ITS -Belgrade

Print

The Higher Education Technical School of Professional Studies in Novi Sad, Serbia

Circulation

100 copies

Publication year

2024

First edition

ISBN-978-86-82744-03-0 (tom)

ISBN-978-86-82744-00-9 (niz)

CIP - Каталогизација у публикацији
Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

616(082)

INTERNATIONAL Multidisciplinary Conference "Challenges of Contemporary Higher Education" (2024 ; Kopaonik)

Book of proceedings. Vol 2 / International Multidisciplinary Conference "Challenges of Contemporary Higher Education" - CCHE 2024, Kopaonik January 29th - February 3rd 2024 ; [organisers] Conference of Academies for Applied Studies in Serbia (CAASS), University Business Academy in Novi Sad, Faculty of Contemporary Arts, Belgrade ; edited by Branko Savić. - 1st ed. - Belgrade : Conference of Academies for Applied Studies in Serbia [i. e.] (CAASS) : University Business Academy in Novi Sad, Faculty of Contemporary Arts, 2024 (Novi Sad : Higher Education Technical School of Professional Studies). - 450 str. : ilustr. ; 24 cm

Tiraž 100. - Str. 1-2: Preface / Branko Savić. - Bibliografija uz svaki rad.

ISBN 978-86-82744-03-0

ISBN 978-86-82744-00-9 (niz)

1. Савић, Бранко, 1969- [уредник] [аутор додатног текста]
а) Медицина -- Зборници

COBISS.SR-ID 139347465

THE INFLUENCE OF YEARS OF WORKING EXPERIENCE ON THE VISUAL-MOTOR COORDINATION OF PHYSIOTHERAPISTS AND OCCUPATIONAL THERAPISTS

Milica Stanić¹, Rastislava Krasnik², Aleksandra Mikov³, Jelena Zvekić Svorcan⁴, Mirjana Kolundžić⁵,

Dajana Dedić Novaković⁶, Željka Popov⁷

Abstract: The study was conducted with the aim of determining whether there is a connection between the years of experience of physiotherapists and occupational therapists and the level of their visuo-motor coordination. Reviewing the available literature, we did not come across a large number of scientific articles dealing with this important topic. During their daily work with patients, healthcare workers encounter numerous professional and emotional challenges, which can affect the level of their visual-motor coordination. Based on the obtained research results, guidelines can be obtained for conducting future research, as well as how it is possible to improve the level of visuo-motor control of health workers.

Key words: physiotherapists, occupational therapists, visual-motor coordination

1. INTRODUCTION

Visual-motor coordination is the ability to match motor output with visual input. It is a complex process of integrating information from the visual and motor systems in order to achieve an optimal movement pattern that is visually accurate and economical in terms of spent energy and time [1], [2].

The daily challenges and specificity of work faced by healthcare workers while working with patients and working in shifts significantly affect the level of visual-motor coordination. The years of work experience of healthcare workers are often related to emotional exhaustion, work capacity, absenteeism, burnout syndrome, and lower level of visual-motor coordination [3], [4].

2. AIM

To assess the impact of years of work experience of physiotherapists and occupational therapists on the level of their visuo-motor coordination.

¹ PhD student, MSc Physiotherapist, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia, Institute of Child and Youth Care of Vojvodina, Novi Sad, Serbia, email: 903013d23@mf.uns.ac.rs

² Associate Professor and MD, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia, Institute of Child and Youth Care of Vojvodina, email: rastislava.krasnik@mf.uns.ac.rs

³ University Professor and MD, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia, Institute of Child and Youth Care of Vojvodina, email: aleksandra.mikov@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁴ Assistant Professor and MD, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Serbia, Special Hospitalc for Rheumatic Diseases, Novi Sad, Serbia, email: jelena.zvekić-svorcan@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁵ MD, Health Center Novi Sad, Serbia, email: kolundzic.mirjana@dzns.rs

⁶ PhD student and MD, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, Onkology Institute of Vojvodina, Sremska Kamenica, Serbia, email: 1414d20@mf.uns.ac.rs

⁷ Phd student and Teaching Associate, Faculty of Medicine, University of Novi Sad, The College of Vocational Studies for the Education of Preschool Teachers and Sports Trainers, Subotica, Serbia, email: 903005d@mf.uns.ac.rs

3. METHODS

The research was conducted as a prospective cross-sectional study, including 25 physiotherapists and occupational therapists, employed at the Clinic for Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation IZZZDIOV Novi Sad in the period from April 15, 2023. until June 15, 2023. The respondents previously signed the informed consent and the consent of the Ethics Committee IZZZDIOV Novi Sad was obtained (part. no.: 17/14-2023). The criteria for not being included in the study were the existence of data on surgery and a injuries of the locomotor system in the last 6 months, subjects who use drugs from the benzodiazepine group and subjects who did not sign consent to participate in the study. Data were obtained using a socio-demographic questionnaire, constructed by the examiner, as well as data obtained using the Hand-Eye Coordination test for the assessment of visuo-motor coordination. To conduct this test, it was required: tennis ball, stopwatch and smooth wall. This test requires the respondents to throw and catch a tennis ball off a wall. The respondents warm up for 10 minutes and stand two meters from a smooth wall. Then the examiner gives the command "go" and starts the stopwatch. The respondent throws a tennis ball with their right hand against the wall and catches it with their left hand, throws the ball with their left hand and catches it with their right hand. This cycle of throwing and catching is repeated for 30 seconds and the examiner counts the number of catches and stops the test after 30 seconds.

Number of chaches is divided into 5 categories: poor (<20), below average (20-24), average (25-29), above average (30-35) and excellent (>35). The test was constructed by Beashel et al. (1997), it is open access and free for academic and non-commercial use [5].

The collected data are presented using descriptive statistical indicators. Mean with standard deviation, as well as minimum and maximum were used. Attributive values are presented using frequencies and percentages. The Mann Whitney U test was used to test statistical significance for two groups of data, and the correlation was determined by the Pearson's correlation coefficient with the use of an appropriate program for statistical data processing (SPSS ver. 26). In all analyses, a value of $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. The obtained results are presented using a tables and with the help of figures (Microsoft Excel) in the program Microsoft Word for Windows MS Office.

4. RESULTS

In this research participated 25 respondents of both sexes, with an average age of 38.28 ± 10.61 years, and an average years of work expirience of 13.74 ± 11.23714 years. Average body height was 170.24 ± 8.53561 , and average body weight was 72.56 ± 8.53561 (Table 1.).

Table 1. Socio-demographic characteristics of the sample

	SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS				
	N	Min	Max	M	SD
Age	25	23	62	37.88	10.5369
Body height	25	158	191	170.24	8.53561
Body weight	25	54	95	72.56	11.26603
Years of work expirience	25	1	38	13.74	11.23714

N-number of respondents, Min-minimum value on the sample,
Max-maximum value on the sample, M-mean value, SD-standard deviation

Almost half of the respondents (48%) had a below average level of hand-eye coordination (Figure 1.).

Figure 1. Level of hand-eye coordination

The correlation between two independent variables (years of work experience and hand-eye coordination test values) was calculated, using the Pearson’s correlation coefficient. The obtained results speaks in favor of the existence of a negative correlation between the two mentioned variables, which is not statistically significant ($p>0.05$) (Table 2.).

Table 2. Correlation between years of work experience and the level of eye-hand coordination

	YEARS OF WORK EXPIRIENCE	
Hand-eye coordination test	N	25
	Pearson’s r	-0,037
	p	0,867

N-number of subjects, Pearson's r-Pearson’s correlation coefficient, p-level of correlation significance

5. DISCUSSION

Visual-motor coordination, when it comes to fine motor skills, includes (a) motor processes, (movements of the eyes, head and hands); (b) sensorial processes (visual, vestibular and somatosensory systems); (c) internal representations of sensory perception and action; and (d) higher-level processes for adaptive and anticipatory aspects of fine motor functions. Visual-motor coordination skills have been found to be correlated with social-emotional functioning and academic skills [1], [2], [6].

Visual-motor coordination requires normal cognitive executive functionality, an ability to transform visual inputs into movement plans and motor-execution skills [1], [6], [7].

Gao et al. (2010) state that the eye-hand coordination process takes place in an organized manner, primarily by finding the focused object visually, then by focusing attention on the object, followed by perceptual recognition of its location, cognitive process, and finally the initiation of movement, using the musculoskeletal system [8].

Choetzee and Pienaar (2013) describe the failure of coordination, difficulty or limitation at the level of motor coordination, which leads to a low level of expected performance, in relation to the chronological age of the respondents [9].

Studying the effects of eye-hand coordination in 42 children aged 5 to 6 years, Candra et al. (2019) concluded that this type of coordination is of great importance when it comes to children's ability to manipulate objects and it was shown that children with a higher level of visuo-motor coordination later, at an older age, have a higher degree of dexterity [10].

In their article, Solano-Ruiz et al. (2013) studied job satisfaction among healthcare workers, which is influenced by gender, age and years of work experience and they determined that the highest level of job dissatisfaction was in the age category of respondents from 35 to 50 years old, as well as among respondents whose work experience was longer than 15 years, which represents the average age and years of work experience of our respondents. Thanks to this work, we can place visuo-motor coordination in the context of (dis)satisfaction with work. If healthcare workers are not satisfied with their work, the level of visuo-motor coordination will consequently decrease [1], [2], [11].

Patel and Bansal (2018) said in their study that if we improve hand eye coordination of people, it will improve their skills and daily functioning. Because, good hand eye coordination increases a person's ability to perform complex movement, respond effectively to external stimuli and create fluent movement. The results of that research indicate that specially designed exercises, during a four-week training session, maintain and increase the development of hand-eye coordination [12].

6. CONSLUSION

Along with the increase in the number of years of work experience for physiotherapists and occupational therapists, there is a reduction in visual-motor coordination.

It is important to know these data in order to be able to conduct further research, to include a larger number of subjects and to assess how the reduction of visuo-motor coordination could be corrected.

7. REFERENCES

- [1] Grillner S. Visuomotor coordination in reaching and Locomotion. *Science*. 1989;245(4923):1209–10.
- [2] Flanagan JR, Johansson RS. Eye–hand coordination during learning of a novel Visuomotor Task. *The Journal of Neuroscience*. 2005;25(39):8833–42.
- [3] Hölzle P, Tatarau C, Hermsdörfer J. Visually Guided Tracking on a Handheld Device: Can It Be Used to Measure Visuomotor Skill in Shift Workers? *Human Factors*. 2014;56(7):1296–1306.
- [4] ML Kaiser, JM Albaret, PA Doudin. Relationship Between Visual-Motor Integration, Eye Hand Coordination, and Quality of Handwriting. *Journal of Occupational Therapy, Schools & Early Intervention*. 2009;2(2):87-95.
- [5] Beashel P, Taylor A. In: Sibson J, editor. *The World of Sport Examined*. First ed. Zagreb, Croatia: Nelson Thornes and Sons; 1997. p. 66.
- [6] Inzelberg R, Schechtman E, Hocherman S. Visuo-motor coordination deficits and motor impairments in parkinson's disease. *PLoS ONE*. 2008;3(11):e3663.
- [7] Fang Y, Wang J, Zhang Y, Qin J. The Relationship of Motor Coordination, Visual Perception, and Executive Function to the Development of 4-6-Year-Old Chinese Preschoolers' Visual Motor Integration Skills. *Biomed Res Int*. 2017;2017:6264254.
- [8] Gao KL, Ng SS, Kwok JW, Chow RT, Tsang WW. Eyehand coordination and its relationship with sensori-motor impairments in stroke survivors. *Journal of Rehabilitation and Medicine*. 2010; 42(4):368–73.

- [9] Coetzee D, Pienaar A E. The effect of visual therapy on the ocular motor control of seven-year old children with developmental coordination disorder (DCD). *Res Dev Disabilities*. 2013; 34(11):4073–84.
- [10] Candra R, Rasyid W, Asnaldi A, Oktarifaldi, Bakhtiar S. Effect of hand-eye coordination on the capability of Children Object Control. *Proceedings of the 1st International Conference of Physical Education (ICPE 2019)*. 2020;460(1):204–7.
- [11] Solano-Ruíz M del, Martínez-Roche ME, Gómez-García CI. Job satisfaction among health care workers: The role of gender and age. *Revista Latino-Americana de Enfermagem*. 2013;21(6):1314–20.
- [12] Patel B, Bansal P. Effect of 4 week exercise program on hand eye coordination. *International Journal of Physical Education, Sports and Health*. 2018;5(4):81–4.